

UNIVERSITY OF HAWAII AT MĀNOA
Institute for Astronomy

Pan-STARRS Project Management System

PS1 Science Goals Statement

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1 Referenced Documents

1.1 Internal Documents

Reference	Title
PSDC-250-001	Pan-STARRS Science Goals Statement (PS4)
PSDC-250-002	Pan-STARRS System Concept Definition (PS4)
PSDC-230-000	PS1 Mission Statement
PSDC-230-001	PS1 Science Goals Statement (This document)
PSDC-230-002	PS1 Science Mission Concept (“mini-DRM/Nutshell”)
PSDC-230-003	PS1 Design Reference Mission (00=old version, to be superseed)
PSDC-230-004	PS1 System Requirements Specification
PSDC-230-005	PS1 Plan of Operations
PSDC-220-001	PS1 Science Consortium Polices
PS1-MOA	PS1 Memorandum of Agreement for the PS1 Science Consortium
PSDC-330-002-00	The Pan-STARRS Filter Set Specifications

2 Scope

2.1 Identification

This document is the Science Goals Statement (SGS) for the Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System (Pan-STARRS) prototype single telescope system, PS1. This SGS is a System-level controlled specification/design description document representing the highest level component of the official Pan-STARRS PS1 engineering specification tree as described in the Pan-STARRS Project Management Plan (PMP, PSDC-110-001).

2.2 System Overview

The University of Hawaii Institute for Astronomy is developing a synoptic survey telescope system, the Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System (Pan-STARRS). Pan-STARRS was initially proposed in response to a USAF AFRL (United States Air Force, Air Force Research Laboratory) Broad Agency Announcement seeking development of "potential dual-use" observatory technology (BAA02-DE-01). The Pan-STARRS concept is based on the goal of constructing an astronomical survey system at a relatively low cost with greater survey capability than all existing survey systems combined. The Pan-STARRS project is now sponsored by the U.S. Air Force under a Cooperative Agreement (CA) with the Pan-STARRS Principal Investigator (PI) and the IfA.

The Pan-STARRS science goals, system performance drivers, and associated system performance requirements for full multi-aperture array are described in the Pan-STARRS Science Goals Statement (PSDC-250-001) and the Pan-STARRS System Concept Definition (PSDC-250-002). The system conceptual design for this final Pan-STARRS Telescope is expected to consist of an array of four 1.8m optical systems, each with a 7 degree² field of view and 1.4 Gigapixel camera, that would then yield a system étendue larger than all existing survey instruments combined. This system is henceforth referred to as PS4.

The Pan-STARRS project, in part due to a suggestion of an external oversight committee, undertook the construction of a prototype telescope, PS1, for the purpose of testing the optical design, detectors, control system, and data reduction pipeline to demonstrate a working system that could be scaled to meet the top level PS4 Science Goals. Therefore the Pan-STARRS project is committed to provide a functioning PS1 system.

In constructing PS1 to demonstrate the potential scalability and evolution towards PS4, the project has also produced a working system that is by itself a significant cyclical sky survey facility. However, in order to realize the full scientific potential of PS1 as a cyclical survey telescope, the operations of the PS1 system has specific needs outside the scope of the USAF Cooperative Agreement. These include: (i) funds for operations, (ii) further software development to extend the base-level pipeline, and (iii) resources for follow-up observations. These resources may be provided by a non-CA federal funds or by a consortium of institutions or private individuals formed to operate the PS1 facility and analyze and publish the results of PS1 observations.

The PS1 system performance will be compared with the PS1 System Requirements Specification (SRS, PSDC-230-004-00) at the PS1 Operational Readiness Reviews (ORRs).

For expediency, we divide the PS1 System Operational Readiness Review (ORR) into three separate ORRs.

2.2.1 Summit Operational Readiness Review. At Summit ORR, the performance of the Telescope, Camera, OTIS, and IPP Subsystems will be presented and compared with those specified in the PS1 System Requirements Specification (SRS, PSDC-230-004-00) of which this document represents the highest level of specification.

2.2.2 MOPS Operational Readiness Review. At MOPS ORR, the performance of the Moving Object Processing System will be presented and compared with those specified in the MOPS SubSystem Requirements Specification (PSDC-530-002-00).

2.2.3 PSPS Operational Readiness Review. At PSPS ORR, the performance of the Published Science Products System (PSPS) will be presented and compared with those specified in the PSPS SubSystem Requirements Specification (PSDC-630-001-00).

At Summit Operational Readiness Review the status of the MOPS and the date for MOPS ORR and the status of PSPS and the date for PSPS ORR will be presented.

Summit ORR is to be scheduled expeditiously, following the completion of PS1 Commissioning and PS1 Pre-Ops. At Summit ORR the PS1 system is either accepted or rejected by the Pan-STARRS Principal Investigator. It is expected that the Principal Investigator will consult with representatives of the the PS1 Science Consortium Board on this decision.

It is up to the PS1 Science Consortium Board to accept the PS1 System as presented at Summit ORR, and decide to begin the PS1 Mission as described outlined in the PS1 Mission Concept Statement (PSDC-230-002-00) under the PS1 Science Consortium Policies and according to the PS1 Operations Plan (PSDC-230-005-00).

It is important to note that PS1 is a research and development prototype, and it is anticipated that there could be variances in meeting the PS1 Requirements and Specifications. The decision to proceed with the PS1 Design Reference Mission will be made by the PS1 Science Consortium Board, and the Consortia MOA will provide all appropriate protections should the Board decide that PS1 performance does not meet the PS1 Requirements and Specifications within allowable variances.

PS1 is sited on the location of the former Lunar Ranging Experiment (LURE) facility at Haleakala Observatory, Maui. The PS1 observatory, and associated project hardware are all property of The Institute for Astronomy, University of Hawaii.

2.3 Document Overview

This Science Goals Statement (SGS) for The Pan-STARRS Telescope #1, PS1 describes the science goals, the key science programs or domain areas, and the minimum set of top-level requirements (TLRs) that define the starting point of the PS1 System Requirements Specification (PSDC-230-002-00). This establishes the engineering requirements flow-down and trace matrix for all PS1 subsystem requirements. This SGS is also the starting point for the PS1 Mission Concept (PSDC-230-003-00), PS1 Design Reference Mission (PSDC-230-003-01), the PS1 Operations Plan (PSDC-230-005-00).

Until the PS1 facility becomes operational and management authority transitions to a non-CA management structure (the PS1 Science Consortium) this document and all PS1 engineering documents are approved and controlled by the CA-funded Pan-STARRS project Management Office. At the time PS1 operations begin, authority for PS1 engineering management resides under the authority of the Pan-STARRS Project Office.

3 Overview of PS1 Science Goals

We are at the threshold of a new step forward in understanding our universe and humanities place within that universe. Three US national decadal reviews have endorsed the scientific desirability of cyclically surveying the night sky. (Astronomy and Astrophysics in the New Millenium, NAS 2001; Connecting Quarks with the Cosmos, NAS 2003; New Frontiers in the Solar System, NAS 2003.). PS1 will constitute the largest step towards that capability in the next several years.

The number of science goals that *can* be met with a system that meets the PS1 Top Level System Requirements described herein are vast, and many, no doubt, have not yet been conceived. Nonetheless the principals involved in developing the Pan-STARRS technology have focused on five science goals that drive the PS1 top level requirements:

- Precision photometric and astrometric survey of stars in the Milky Way and the Local Group;
- Surveying our Solar System, including searching for Potentially Hazardous Objects amongst Near Earth Asteroids;
- New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter;
- Exploration and categorization of the astrophysical time domain, including, but not limited to, explosive transients, microlensing events in M31, and a transit search for exo-planets; and
- Providing a development platform for prototyping PS4 components, subsystems, and survey strategy.

Amongst these top level goals, the highest priority for PS1 is the first: a precision astrometric and photometric catalog of stellar objects. This is a necessary prerequisite for the precision image registration, stacking, and image subtraction that are required to meet the all the other science drivers. The resulting PS1 catalog and PS1 static sky images are required for PS4 operations.

3.1 Science Goals that drive PS1 System Requirements

3.1.1 Precision photometric and astrometric survey of stars in the Milky Way and Local Group

A 3π steradian photometric and astrometric catalog in 5 bandpasses g, r, i, z, y of unprecedented precision and accuracy can be generated with PS1. This will have at least 20 to 30 times better astrometry and photometry than the USNO-B catalog. Compared with SDSS, the PS1 reference star catalog will cover 5 times the area, with 5 times the astrometric accuracy. It will discover new stars in the solar neighborhood by parallax and proper motion. The z and y bandpasses are particularly sensitive to nearby L and T class dwarf stars, and brown dwarfs. This survey will enable detailed studies of stellar populations of star clusters and associations, identification of stellar streams in the Galaxy (which probe the formation and dynamical history of our Galaxy), studies of young stellar objects and star forming regions, and galactic tracers such as RR Lyrae stars, carbon stars, and Cepheids.

The photometric and astrometric survey also serves the practical purpose of laying down the grid by which Pan-STARRS and other sky survey projects can register its images both for stacking them and for finding moving and stationary transients.

3.1.2 Surveying our Solar System and the Search for Potentially Hazardous Objects

PS1 together with its Image Processing Pipeline and Moving Object Processing System will be capable of finding Potentially Hazardous Objects of to 1000 meters diameter at a distance of 2.5 AU at opposition, or equivalently, asteroids of 140 meters diameter at a distance of 0.7 AU. A complete census of PHO's to a given magnitude may be possible with the PS1 3π survey, but that is not a requirement.

Furthermore, PS1 will obtain an incomplete, but statistically well-sampled catalog of major sub-populations of the solar system's small bodies, including main belt asteroids, Trojans, Centaurs, Trans-Neptunian Objects, Kuiper Belt Objects, Comets, and possibly new planets.

3.1.3 New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter

A combination of powerful observational techniques will be used to place firm new constraints on the nature of the Dark Energy and the Dark Matter in the universe, and on the geometrical nature of our universe. These include (i) detection and precision photometry of cosmologically distant SNIa, (ii) weak lensing measurements that determine the total mass distribution on cosmological scales, and (iii) measurements of the distribution of massive galaxies (the observed $P(k)$) which can be compared with the perturbations imprinted on the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB). (iv) LSS-biasing

3.1.4 Exploration and Categorization of the Time Domain: Explosive Transients, μ Lensing, and Stellar Transits

PS1 will systematically investigate the time domain with unprecedented area coverage, sensitivity, and time resolution. Characterization of the magnitude, color, and time domain for a host of astrophysical phenomena can be expected to unveil new phenomena and shed light on transient and variable events including flare stars, cataclysmic variables, magnetic white dwarfs, nova, supernova, gamma-ray bursters, orphan afterglows, accretion onto other compact objects, and black hole accretion events. PS1 will also search for exo-planets using the stellar transit method, and for micro-lensing events in M31.

3.1.5 Provide a development platform for prototyping PS4 components, subsystems, and survey strategy

The Pan-STARRS project, in part due to a suggestion of an external oversight committee, undertook the construction of a prototype telescope, PS1, for the purpose of testing the optical design, detectors, control system, and data reduction pipeline to demonstrate a working system that could be scaled to meet the top level PS4 Science Goals. Therefore the Pan-STARRS project is committed to provide a functioning PS1 system.

In constructing PS1 to demonstrate the potential scalability and evolution towards PS4, the project has also produced a working system

3.2 PS1 Key Science Project Areas

While the number of scientific projects that can be accomplished with PSw is vast, and we anticipate new ones will be added as the mission progresses and new ideas arise, below we list the currently envisioned PS1 Key Science Projects or Domain Areas. These are major scientific areas of study where it is expected that PS1 can make significant advances, and where the members of the PS1 Science Consortium are expected to dedicate substantial effort and resources, including in many cases followup or complementary observations to the PS1 Surveys. It is expected that new ones will be added as the PS1 Mission unfolds. The leadership, organization and policies under which these key projects are administered are spelled out in the PS1 Science Consortium Policies document.

Below are the initial PS1 Key Science Areas. The assignment of Leaders and Co-Leaders of these are listed in the "Organization of PS1 Key Science Areas", which is one of the defining documents of the PS1SC Memorandum of Agreement.

- 3.2.1 Populations of objects in the Inner Solar System**
- 3.2.2 Populations of objects in the Outer Solar System (Beyond Jupiter)**
- 3.2.3 Low Mass Stars, Brown Dwarfs, and Young Stellar Objects**
- 3.2.4 A Search for Exo-planets by a dedicated Stellar Transit Survey**
- 3.2.5 Structure of the Milky Way and Local Group**
- 3.2.6 A Dedicated Deep Survey of M31**
- 3.2.7 Massive Stars and Supernovae Progenitors**
- 3.2.8 Cosmology Investigations with Variables and Explosive Transients**
- 3.2.9 Galaxy Properties**
- 3.2.10 Active Galactic Nuclei and High Redshift Quasars**
- 3.2.11 Cosmological Lensing**
- 3.2.12 Large Scale Structure**

Details on the science goals, programs, projects, and follow-up observations of these Key Science Areas are listed on the PS1SC "wiki" pages.

3.3 Other PS1 Science Projects

A great many other PS1 Science Projects are possible that either do not fit directly within one of these domains, or crosses boundaries between these domains. The desire of the PS1 Science Consortium is to maximize the science from PS1, and this includes rapid response to new ideas to extract science from the PS1 surveys, and if necessary adjust the surveys. The policies for addressing new ideas, and new key projects or domain areas are expressed in the PS1 Science Consortium Policies document, and the PS1 Science Consortium Memorandum of Agreement (MOA).

4 PS1 Top Level Requirements

4.1 Overview of PS1 Requirements

The primary mission goals above require a sensitivity that is at present only possible with silicon ccd technology. This limits the operational bandpass on the long wavelength side to a wavelength of 1036 nm due to the band gap in silicon. The short wavelength side could, in principle extend down to the atmospheric absorption cut-off of $\approx 300\text{nm}$, however the practicalities of obtaining the required optical performance and comparable sensitivity over significantly more than a factor of two in wavelength limits PS1 optical performance to $\approx 400\text{nm}$ on the short wavelength side. This operational

bandpass has been divided into five broad band filters g, r, i, z, y . The choice, comparison with other recent instruments, and the technical specification of these bandpasses are provided in "The Pan-STARRS Filter Set Specifications", PSDC-330-002-00. The system may also possess a "w filter" approximately equal to a $g + r + i = w$ filter to test the scheduling, utilization, and performance of such a filter.

The science requirements presented in Section 4.2 lead to engineering requirements and design decisions for the PS1 System. The engineering requirements that flow from the science requirements, plus allocated system requirements, are presented in the "PS1 System Subsystem Specification", PSDC-230-003-00.

4.2 PS1 Science Requirements

- 4.2.1 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an astrometric catalog with peak errors in absolute astrometry not to exceed 0.1 arcseconds for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.
- 4.2.2 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an astrometric catalog with peak errors in relative astrometric accuracy of ≤ 0.01 arcseconds for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.
- 4.2.3 The PS1 filter set shall consist of g, r, i, z, y filters with the approximate bandpasses specified in Table 4.2.3.
Note: this requirement could be considered allocated to system design, but it appears here at the science level because the definition of the PS1 science mission assumes the constraint of the optical response of the CCDs combined with the necessity for sufficient colors to enable determination of photometric redshifts.

Table 1: PS1 filter set bandpasses

Filter	Bandpass (nm)
g	405–550
r	552–689
i	691–815
z	815–915
y	967-1024

- 4.2.4 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an associated photometric catalog with absolute photometric precision of ≤ 0.015 magnitudes (rms) in g band across 3π steradians for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.
- 4.2.5 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an associated photometric catalog with absolute photometric precision of ≤ 0.010 magnitudes (rms) in r band across 3π steradians for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.
- 4.2.6 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an associated photometric catalog with absolute photometric precision of ≤ 0.010 magnitudes (rms) in i band across 3π steradians for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.

- 4.2.7 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an associated photometric catalog with absolute photometric precision of ≤ 0.010 magnitudes (rms) in z band across 3π steradians for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.
- 4.2.8 The PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce an associated photometric catalog with absolute photometric precision of ≤ 0.02 magnitudes (rms) in y band across 3π steradians for stellar objects for whom the dominant source of noise in a single image is from the the Poissonian noise of that star's own signal.
- 4.2.9 The PS1 system image processing shall remove the image foregrounds to a level that results in residual systematics less than 1% of the background level.
- 4.2.10 The PS1 system shall provide data and engineering metadata sufficient for post analysis to determine the likelihood of the sky surface brightness $f_{AB}(\alpha, \delta)$ integrated over the passband for each filter.
Note: The likelihood is the probability of the data given the hypothesis that the sky surface brightness is $f_{AB}(\alpha, \delta)$, see PSDC-200-011-00 for the data product. This information is necessary to achieve any science relying on static sky characterization. In the limit that the sky pixelization is small, this requires, for each passband, both a "signal map" and "exposure map" (these effectively determine the most likely surface brightness at each point on the sky as well as the associated uncertainty).
- 4.2.11 The PS1 system shall provide data and engineering metadata sufficient to determine the effective point spread function (PSF) at each point in the sky.
Note: This capability is required by the WL and the PHO Census science programs.
- 4.2.12 For objects identified as solar system objects, the PS1 system shall generate data (including metadata) and provide processing to produce a minimum set of object parameters for each object consisting of the orbital elements, an Earth-object MOID, and the equivalent of an absolute H magnitude.
- 4.2.13 The PS1 system shall be capable of detecting a 1000 meter asteroid at a distance of 2.5 AU at opposition, or, equivalently a 140 meter asteroid at a distance of 0.72 AU at opposition.
Note: The equations by which these limits are derived, and the assumptions regarding the properties of the bodies are given in the the PS1 Mission Concept document, PSDC-230-002-00).
- 4.2.14 The PS1 system shall produce data (including metadata) sufficient to characterize the systematic and random uncertainties in the determination of photometric redshifts.
- 4.2.15 The PS1 system shall produce data (including metadata) sufficient to characterize the systematic and random uncertainties in the determination of weak lensing parameters of galaxies from static sky images (KSB - ϵ , psm , psh , σ , i.e., ellipticity, smear polarizability, shear polarizability, and window function radius, respectively)
- 4.2.16 The PS1 system shall produce data (including metadata) sufficient to characterize the systematic and random uncertainties in the derived absolute photometry of fields observed for cosmological Type Ia SN.
- 4.2.17 PS1 shall be able to detect and catalog transients within thirty (30) minutes of the actual exposure time.
- 4.2.18 The PS1 system shall have the capability to provide alerts within thirty (30) minutes of the actual exposure time for detected transients in regions of the sky where a prepared static sky image exists.
- 4.2.19 PS1 shall be capable of copying transient detections to local storage systems, should they be provided, within thirty-five (35) minutes of the actual exposure time.

5 Requirements Traceability

5.1 PS1 Science Requirements vs. PS1 Science Goals

Table 2: Requirements Traceability

PS1 Science Reqmt.	Caption	PS1 Science Goal	Caption
4.2.1	PS1 Filter Set	3.1.1	Photometry and Astrometry Survey
4.2.1	PS1 Filter Set	3.1.3	New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter
4.2.1	PS1 Filter Set	3.1.4	Exploration of the time domain
4.2.1	PS1 Filter Set	3.1.4	Provide development for PS4
4.2.2	Astrometric precision and accuracy	3.1.1	Photometry and Astrometry Survey
4.2.2	Astrometric Precision	3.1.2	Search for PHO's (image differencing)
4.2.2	Astrometric Precision	3.1.3	Dark Energy and Dark Matter (image difference)
4.2.2	Astrometric Precision	3.1.4	Exploration of the time domain (image difference)
4.2.2	Astrometric Precision	3.1.5	Provide development for PS4 (stacked image)
4.2.3-7	Photometric precision and accuracy	3.1.1	Photometry and Astrometry Survey
4.2.3-7	Photometric precision and accuracy	3.1.3	New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter
4.2.3-7	Photometric precision and accuracy	3.1.4	Exploration of the time domain
4.2.3-7	Photometric precision and accuracy	3.1.5	Provide development for PS4
4.2.8	Solar system object parameters	3.1.2	Search for PHO's
4.2.9	Asteroid discovery	3.1.2	Search for PHO's
4.2.10	Weak lensing parameter uncertainties	3.1.3	New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter
4.2.11	Photometric redshift uncertainties	3.1.3	New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter
4.2.12	Light curve uncertainties	3.1.3	New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter
4.2.13	Transient alerts	3.1.4	Exploration of the time domain
4.2.14	Serving transient alerts	Allocated	

6 Acronyms

CA - Cooperative Agreement

CAM - Gigapixel Camera Group

IPP - Image Processing Pipeline

GPC1 - Gigapixel Camera #1

MOID - Minimum Orbital Intersection Distance

MOA - Memorandum of Agreement

MOPS - Moving Object Processing System

MPG - Max Planck Gesellschaft (Max Planck Society)

ORR - Operational Readiness Review

OTIS - Observatory, Telescope, & Instrument Software

Pan-STARRS - Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System

PHO - Potentially Hazardous Objects

PI - Principal Investigator

PS1 - Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System Telescope #1

PS4 - Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System Telescope #4

PSPS - Published Science Products System (database)

TC3 - Test Camera #3

TTI - Transient Time Interval

TEL - PS1 Telescope Group